

SMART FISHWAYS

W1 – WLN sensor network development

D1.1 Water level monitoring sensor network v1

Abstract

The "Water level monitoring sensor network" deliverable contains a detailed description of the developed sensor network to capture the hydraulic behaviour of stepped fishways and assess their performance under different hydrological scenario.

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Project information

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<i>Project title</i>	Adapting fishways to hydrological and climatic uncertainty
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<i>Abstract</i>	<p>Modern society currently requires large volumes of fresh water. The result is the installation of river barriers, causing the fragmentation of habitats as well as changes in the ecology of freshwater systems. Stepped fishways can allow fish to move freely up rivers to complete their life cycle. However, the variability of rivers modifies the hydraulic conditions within fishways, affecting the free movement of fish.</p> <p>Smart Fishways is an EU-funded project, which aims to assess the effect of hydrological variability on stepped fishways and to develop a technological and methodological framework to monitor fishways' performance in real-time. By combining fish biology, hydraulics and sensor networks, a new generation of smart fishways will be created, capable of self-deciding their optimal configuration.</p>
<i>Work Package number</i>	W1 WLN sensor network development
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Document Control Page

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1. Introduction

One of the first objectives of Smart Fishway project was to develop a technological framework to monitor the hydraulics of fishways in real-time. To achieve this, a water level monitoring sensor network has been developed. By measuring water levels in a fishway it is possible to infer other relevant hydraulic parameters (e.g. velocity, volumetric power dissipation, turbulence, etc.), after assessing fishway performance.

The following document describes the developed network taking as reference the recently published article “A Step to Smart Fishways: An Autonomous Obstruction Detection System Using Hydraulic Modeling and Sensor Networks” [1].

2. Fishway Hydraulics: Why measure water level?

The flow structure inside a stepped fishway is three-dimensional (3D) and varies according to the connections at the cross-walls. However, the water level distribution along the fishway pools (1D performance) can be easily calculated via an iterative bottom-up calculus considering 1) the boundary conditions upstream (discharge or water-level) and downstream (water-level), 2) discharge equations in the cross-wall-connections and 3) the basic geometrical parameters of the fishway [2,3]. In this sense, the only unknown or variable parameters to solve the water-level distribution in each pool are the river water levels both upstream and downstream of the fishway. After the water level distribution is calculated or measured, more complex variables can be directly estimated (such as the maximum velocity at the connections or the volumetric power dissipation in the pool).

To describe any of the working scenarios in a fishway (either uniform and non-uniform) it is possible to use two sets of equations [2]: set 1, Poleni’s equation [4] (Eq. 1) together with Villemonte’s submergence coefficient [5] (Eq. 2) to describe the performance of notches and slots, and, set 2, the orifice equation derived from Torricelli’s law [6] (Eq. 3) together with a discharge coefficient [7–10] to describe the flow through an orifice. In each of the cross-walls, the total discharge can be expressed as the sum of the individual flows through the different connections.

$$Q = \frac{2}{3} \cdot C_s \cdot b \cdot h_1^{1.5} \cdot \sqrt{2 \cdot g} \quad (1)$$

$$C_s = \beta_0 \left[1 - \left(\frac{h_2}{h_1} \right)^{1.5} \right]^{\beta_1} \quad (2)$$

$$Q = C_o \cdot b_o \cdot a_o \cdot \sqrt{2 \cdot g \cdot \Delta H} \quad (3)$$

where g stands for the gravity acceleration, h_1 is the water level upstream the cross-wall (h_1') deducting the sill height (p), h_2 is the water level upstream a cross-wall deducting p , b is the width of notches, slots, or orifices, a is the height of the orifice, C (C_s and C_o) stands for the discharge coefficients and β_0 and β_1 are coefficients which depend on the geometry of the slot or notch and pool dimensions. Coefficient values for multiple fishway design as well as the calculation procedure can be found in [2].

Thus, water levels inside the fishway are a direct reflection of their working performance and by measuring them we could detect abnormal performances and characterize their full hydraulics.

3. The sensor network

Considering that fishway hydraulic performance can be estimated only by observing water levels, our main objective was to develop a sensor network able to monitor this variable. Although there are multiple alternatives to measure the water levels, those based on ultrasonic sensors have multiple

advantages [11]. This type of sensor does not need to interact directly with the water, which reduces the sealing requirements and its maintenance. Likewise, contrary to other alternatives such as pressure sensor probes, ultrasonic sensors are installed outside the water, which allows achieving more compact designs integrating into a single unit the sensors, wireless communications, and removable energy sources like solar.

In addition, considering the number of nodes of the network, i.e. sensors to be deployed (a maximum of one sensor per pool), the high cost of commercial sensors (≤ 400 €), and the disadvantages of closed source technologies (e.g. they do not allow the custom programming), a new low-cost ultrasound-based node has been developed:

The desired basic design characteristics for the new device were:

- It needs to be able to measure precisely water levels (at least centimeter accuracy).
- It has to be able to transmit wirelessly the information to a central gateway.
- It has to be able to work in conjunction with other sensors autonomously.
- It needs to be solar powered for a long time persistence.
- It has to be low-cost technology (< 130 €, considering material and assembly costs).

Considering these basic characteristics, the sensor network architecture is described in the following sections.

3.1. Node hardware

The network is composed of 1) multiple water level monitoring nodes installed over the different pools of a fishway and 2) a central gateway, which communicates with the nodes individually, runs the algorithms, collects the data, triggers the alarms, and transmits the information to an online server. An alternative use case of similar start network architecture can be found in [12].

Node's principal component is an Atmel ATSAMD21G18 microcontroller (Arduino compatible [13]). This microcontroller is connected to 1) a Long Range (LoRa) RFM95 radio module and a secure digital (SD) card via serial peripheral interface (SPI) connection, and 2) to a real-time clock (RTC, DS3231) and an ultrasonic sensor (JSN-SR04T) via an inter-integrated circuit (I2C) connection (Figura 1a). Likewise, an electronic power switch (Pololu 2808) makes it possible to control its ON/OFF cycles using RTC alarms. All components are soldered to a printed circuit board protected in a watertight (IP68) acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) housing (150x100x70 mm). The system is powered by a 18650 Li-Ion battery, which is charged by a solar panel (6V, 1W) attached to the ABS box (Figure 1b).

Figure 1. The architecture of the node. a) Connections. b) Ultrasound node.

Figure 2. PCB board developed for the project. The board serves as a testing platform for different electronic configurations.

3.1.1. Detailed specifications

Table 1. Default ultrasonic sensor specifications. The device is compatible with different sensors and ranges.

Sensor type	JSN-SR04T
Range	250 a 4500 mm
Accuracy	±10 mm
Resolution	2 mm
Respuesta del sensor	40 kHz

Table 2. Logger module specifications

Real-time clock	DS3231 Accuracy ±2ppm from 0°C to +40°C Accuracy ±3.5ppm from -40°C to +85°C
Battery	Battery type: 18650, rechargeable 3.7 Volt lithium, user-replaceable
Battery Life*	Solar-powered. Without solar more than 1 year with 5 minute or greater logging interval under a temperature of 20°C
Memory (SD-card)	8 – 246 GB, standard SD card
Weight	Approximately 200 g in air
Dimensions	150x100x70 mm
Housing materials	Polycarbonate tubing; POM caps; Stainless steel bolts and sensor; Viton and Buna-N O-rings;
Logging interval	Configurable.
Battery indication	Battery voltage is logged in the data file
Environment Rating	IP68

*Tested duration. Higher durations are expected.

Table 3. Default communication module configuration. The device is compatible with different modes of communication.

Sensor type	RFM95
Protocol*	LoRa - radio
Range	> 10 km (in optimal conditions)

3.2. Gateway hardware

The gateway consists of a small single-board computer (Raspberry Pi 4). This computer is connected to an Atmel ATSAMD21G18 microcontroller with an integrated LoRa RFM95 radio module and a 4G

modem via serial connection. The computer is powered by a 30 A regulator connected to a 12 V battery and a solar panel of 80 W.

3.3. Software

The node and the microcontroller connected to the gateway are programmed in C using the Arduino integrated development environment (IDE) [13]. The single-board computer is running the Raspberry Pi operating system (OS) with scheduled Python scripts (Figure 3). The code allows encrypted communication between nodes and the gateway. Each node has its address, which allows the gateway to identify each one and synchronize their transmission cycles (i.e. the gateway asks for data to each address).

In the programmed workflow, the gateway asks for data to a particular node, the node collects 15 distance measurements, discards possible invalid samples, computes the median, saves the data in the SD card, and transmits the information to the gateway. If the transmission is successful, the gateway returns a new wake-up time to the node, which configures a new wake-up alarm in the node and switches it off. This procedure allows to 1) save power in the nodes by switching them off, 2) synchronize the data transmission, and 3) control the sampling rate by the gateway. If a particular node is unresponsive, the gateway recursively tries to communicate with it during a programmable number of cycles (2 by default). After, if the communication is still not successful, it triggers a management alarm and continues with the rest of the nodes (Figure 3).

Once the gateway has collected a sample for each node, it runs an obstruction detection algorithm (depending on the active number of nodes) and triggers an obstruction alarm if this exists. Finally, data is saved in a local database (MySQL) as well as an online server (HTTPS queries + MySQL), for long time assessment (Figure 3). Further details on the online dashboard architecture and workflows can be found in [12].

Figure 3. The general software architecture of the sensor network

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